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Mobility of potentially toxic elements in family garden soils of the Riotinto mining area.

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1 **Mobility of potentially toxic elements in family garden soils of the Riotinto mining**
2 **area.**

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9 **Highlights (3-5)**

- 10 • To determine the local background is necessary to assess anthropogenic
11 contamination
- 12 • Soil properties reduce the mobility of PTEs
- 13 • Competition of organic matter for sorption sites enhance As mobility
- 14 • More efforts are necessary to introduce mobility tests the in health risk assessment

15 **Abstract**

16 Agricultural soils in mining areas usually accumulate potentially toxic elements (PTEs)
17 that can become a health risk to humans by entering the trophic chain. In this study, five
18 small agricultural plots close to Riotinto mines (SW Spain) were studied, with the aims
19 of comparing the concentration of PTEs with respect to the regional (South Portuguese
20 Zone) baseline and conducting availability studies in order to determine the
21 contamination of soils. Chemical composition, total and clay mineralogy, and edaphic
22 parameters were determined in topsoil and subsoil samples to characterize the soils, and
23 single extractions were conducted to assess the mobility. The mineralogy of the soils was
24 composed of quartz and phyllosilicates, with small amounts of feldspars and occasionally
25 containing hematite and calcite. The texture ranged from sandy to silty loam, the pH was
26 slightly acidic, and high contents of organic matter were found. Total concentrations of
27 trace elements correlated with the texture, the content in iron oxy-hydroxides and the pH.
28 The values of As, Pb, Cu, and Zn exceeded the regional baseline even in sites unaffected
29 by mining. The results suggest that a widespread sampling is necessary to determine the
30 local background. The most water-soluble element was As, due to the competition of
31 organic matter for sorption sites. The content of Cu, Cr and Zn extracted with different

32 methods were higher in sandy soils with low iron oxy-hydroxides content.
33 Monoammonium phosphate and EDTA extractions seemed to remove elements from
34 organic matter and iron oxy-hydroxides. The extracted fractions of As and metals reached
35 up to 10-30 wt%. Despite the high total concentrations of the element in soils, they
36 generally showed low available proportions, especially with water and ammonium acetate
37 extractants. The results suggest that the soils are not necessarily a risk to humans and
38 higher investigation efforts are necessary to assess the availability of PTEs and their
39 transfer to plants.

40

41

42 **Keywords:** minesoil; potentially toxic elements; chemical extraction; agricultural soils;
43 Riotinto mine

44

45 **1. Introduction**

46 Exploitation of mineral resources is one of the major activities contaminating the soil by
47 trace elements. At low concentrations, some of these elements are essential for organisms,
48 but at high concentrations they can be toxic. Due to this, they are generally considered as
49 potentially toxic elements (PTEs) (Adriano, 2001; Adamo et al., 2014).

50 Currently, the standard way to assess the contamination by PTEs is to compare the total
51 concentration in soil with some guideline values. Some of these values are known as
52 screening soil levels (SSL), which indicates the level below which no health risk to
53 humans is expected (Carlson, 2007). If the concentration is higher than the SSL, a health
54 risk assessment must be performed to study the possibility of humans being affected by
55 that pollution (Gabari and Fernández-Caliani, 2017).

56 SSL are calculated based on the risk to human health and ecosystems, according to
57 toxicological models and exposure to pollutants. However, SSL range even in several
58 orders of magnitude in different countries. These differences depend on socio-cultural,
59 political, and scientific aspects (Carlson, 2007). Moreover, SSL do not take into account
60 the geochemical background, which can under- or overestimate anthropogenic
61 contamination. The background changes between sites depending on the lithology or
62 geological characteristics (Horckmans et al., 2005; Galán et al., 2008; Cabral-Pinto et al.,

63 2017; Reinmann et al., 2018), so many authors have suggested that guideline values
64 should be defined according to the regional geochemical background (Horckmans et al.,
65 2005; Jarva et al., 2010; Galán et al., 2019; Reinmann et al., 2018). In complex areas such
66 as mining sites, it is difficult to differentiate anthropogenic contamination from geogenic
67 anomalies. In such cases, determining the local background is needed to evaluate
68 anthropogenic contamination (Horckmans et al., 2005; González et al., 2011; Galán et al.,
69 2014; Rothwell and Cooke, 2015).

70 One more reason the actual SSL are not completely satisfactory for human risk evaluation
71 is because they are based on total concentrations of PTEs instead of the bioavailable
72 fractions (McLaughlin et al, 2000; Clemente et al., 2008; Galán et al., 2019). It is well
73 known that the hazard of pollution depends on the mobility and bioavailability of PTEs
74 (Adriano, 2001; Kabata-Pendias, 2004; Adamo and Zampella, 2018; Entwistle et al.,
75 2019). The total concentration in soil represents the worst possible situation, and it can
76 overestimate the risk. The mobility and bioavailability of PTEs depend on the chemical
77 nature and physical characteristics of the trace element, the soil properties and the
78 geochemical environment, and the ability of plants to absorb the element and translocate
79 it to edible parts (McLaughlin et al, 2000; Adriano, 2001; Kabata-Pendias, 2004;
80 Entwistle et al., 2019).

81 To assess the mobility and bioavailability of PTEs in soil, different types of chemical
82 extractions are used including mineral and organic acids, chelating agents, buffered
83 solutions, neutral salts and other extractants (Quevauviller et al., 1998; Kabata-Pendias,
84 2004; Feng et al., 2005; Fang et al., 2007; Anjos et al., 2012). Unfortunately, there is no
85 universal test for assessing bioavailability, which is one of the reasons why it is not a
86 more common practice in the evaluation of potentially polluted soils (McLaughlin et al.,
87 2000; Sauvé et al., 2000; Anjos et al., 2012). Moreover, recent investigations not only
88 take into account the mobility of the pollutant, but how they are handled in the body,
89 according to bioaccessibility tests (Fernández-Caliani et al., 2019).

90 In a previous study, Galán et al. (2019) proposed a methodological approach for the
91 evaluation of soil pollution in complex areas such as mining sites. The approach is based
92 on the comparison of total contents and mobile fraction of PTEs in the potentially polluted
93 soils with the regional and local background, the influence of the soil properties and, when
94 necessary, the health risk assessment.

95 In this study, agricultural soils of Nerva, a locality that forms part of the Riotinto mining
96 region of South-western Spain, were sampled and analyzed for soil properties and heavy
97 metal concentration. Copper, lead, zinc, silver, and gold have been mined from Riotinto
98 over thousands of years. Since the 19th century, 20 km³ of land has been covered by waste
99 rock due to the excessive mining. These rocks can be a large source of PTEs to the
100 environment. At the end of the 20th century the mining district of Riotinto closed. This
101 caused the growth of an intensive agriculture industry based on citrus and other fruit trees
102 cultivated over leptosols developed on slates. Previous studies have shown that both the
103 bioavailability of PTEs and their transfer to plants is low, so they do not pose a health
104 risk (Romero et al., 2012). However, a traditional agriculture of family gardens for owner
105 consumption is quite common in sandy soils developed on slopes and small valleys. These
106 soils show high concentrations of PTEs with high bioavailability, since they have been
107 affected by an intense, historical pollution (Madejón et al., 2011; Romero et al., 2012;
108 Romero-Baena et al., 2018; Fernández-Caliani et al., 2019).

109 The regional baseline of the area determined in previous studies showed high values of
110 As (25mg/kg), Cu (32mg/kg), Pb (38mg/kg), and Zn (76mg/kg) in soils of the South
111 Portuguese Zone (SPZ), where the Iberian Pyrite Belt and Riotinto mines are included.
112 These values are above thresholds in Andalusia and in most of the world. However, the
113 local background has not been previously determined in this area, particularly in soils
114 where the family gardens are located.

115 The objectives are:

- 116 1) To assess the content of PTEs in garden soils, to compare with the regional
117 baseline and SSL, and to assess the need of establishing the local background.
- 118 2) To assess the use of mobility-availability assays in order to determine possible
119 hazards to humans from soils of the Riotinto mining area.

120

121 **2. Materials and Methods**

122 2.1. Sampling and materials

123 Five gardens (RT 1 – RT 5) were sampled at the locality of Nerva, next to the Riotinto
124 mining district (Figure 1). While most of the soils in the area are leptosols developed over
125 slates, family gardens are usually located on slopes and small valleys, after application of

126 manure and, probably, other amendments such as carbonates. The sites were selected
127 according to the distance to the mining area. Sites RT 1 – RT 3 were close to an area
128 flooded in the past by the breakage of a tailing impoundment. These sites were located
129 towards the top of a hill (RT 1) and down to the valley (RT 3). Sites RT 4 and RT 5 were
130 located far from the mining area and, *a priori*, not affected directly by mining activities.

131 From each site, one sample was collected from the topsoil (0-20 cm) and the subsoil (20-
132 40 cm), respectively. Concerning the topsoil, 5 subsamples collected at a central point
133 and 1 m long in cross directions were mixed to make a composite sample. The subsoil
134 sample was collected from the central point. Most of the samples visually showed a silty-
135 clayey texture, except for site RT 1, where a sandy texture was found, particularly at the
136 subsoil level (sample RT 1-2).

137 Soil samples were dried for about 4 weeks in open air and part of the sample was kept
138 wet in the refrigerator. Dried samples were disaggregated using a rolling pin and passed
139 through a 2 mm sieve. The gravel fraction (>2 mm) was discarded. About 20 g of ≤ 2 mm
140 sample were milled using an agate ball milling machine for 20 minutes at 250 rpm, to
141 pass through a 100 μm sieve, and stored in plastic containers for chemical analysis. 2 g
142 of this fraction was powdered using an agate mortar and passed to a size of 50 μm for
143 mineralogical analysis.

144 2.2. Chemical Analysis

145 Samples of $\leq 100 \mu\text{m}$ were analyzed using a Panalytical Axios X-ray fluorescence (XRF)
146 spectrometer, at the central research facilities of the University of Sevilla (CITIUS). Total
147 concentrations for major (Al, Ca, Fe, K, Mg, Na, P, S, Si, and Ti) and trace elements (As,
148 Cr, Cu, Ni, Pb, and Zn) were determined and compared against Fischer pattern 603-683
149 (for major elements) and GEOPT 24 and 28 (trace elements). The limits of detection and
150 quantification for the principle major elements and trace elements can be seen in **Table**
151 **1**.

152 2.3. Mineralogy

153 Total mineralogy was studied by X-ray diffraction (XRD) using a Bruker D8 Advance
154 A25 diffractometer with Cu-K α radiation at 40 kV and 30 mA, at the CITIUS facilities.
155 About 1 g of soil milled <50 μm was placed in side-loaded sample holders in order to
156 guarantee random powders. The holders were scanned from 3 to 70° 2 θ at a rate of 0.03°

157 20 step intervals and 1 s step time. The assessment of mineral content was estimated by
158 the reflection power method (values used for the reflection power calculated by Galán et
159 al., 1973; Martín Pozas, 1978). For clay mineral identification, the <2 µm fraction were
160 obtained by sedimentation and prepared in oriented aggregates, and then subjected to
161 solvation with ethylene glycol and thermal treatment at 550°C for 2 h (Moore and
162 Reynolds, 1997).

163 2.4. Soil Parameters

164 The texture was determined by laser diffraction with a Malvern Mastersizer 2000
165 instrument in the <2 mm fraction. The soil pH was determined in a soil-water suspension
166 of a 1:2.5 ratio using calibrated Crison electrodes. The total organic content was
167 determined by oxidation with potassium dichromate in a strong acid medium (Walkley–
168 Black’s method, in Pansu and Gautheyrou, 2006), the carbonate content was measured
169 by the Bernard calcimetry method. Humidity of soils was calculated by weight loss after
170 oven total drying.

171 The content of amorphous and crystalline iron oxy-hydroxides was assessed by reduction
172 of iron(III) with ammonium oxalate according to procedures described in steps 3 and 4 at
173 Dold (2003). The ferrous solutions were oxidized with phenanthroline to form an orange
174 complex, and then measured in duplicate by UV spectrophotometry at $\lambda = 510\text{nm}$. A
175 standard solution of iron (III) nitrate was prepared in order to create a calibration curve.
176 The extracted iron in wt% was calculated from the solid/liquid ratio used in the extraction
177 procedure.

178 2.5 Mobility-availability experiments

179 Single extraction solutions were used in this study to assess the bioavailability of trace
180 elements:

181 *Water extraction*

182 Water extraction has been usually applied in single and sequential extraction procedures
183 to assess the soluble and most mobile fraction of trace elements. This extraction simulates
184 the proportion of trace elements that can lixiviate with rain water and the fraction that is
185 available for uptake by plants (Dold, 2003; Anawar et al., 2006; Anjos et al., 2012; Abreu
186 et al., 2014). A mixture of 1 g of soil per 10 mL of deionized water was shaken for 24

187 hours and vacuum filtered through a $\leq 0.2 \mu\text{m}$ membrane filter. Then the solutions were
188 adjusted to pH 2 using concentrated nitric acid.

189 *Monoammonium phosphate extraction*

190 A 0.05 M $\text{NH}_4\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$ solution was used to assess As bioavailability. Phosphate competes
191 with arsenate for adsorption sites in soils so $\text{NH}_4\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$ can extract specifically-bound As
192 without causing significant mineral dissolution (Wenzel et al., 2001). A mixture of 1g of
193 soil per 25 mL of solution was shaken for 16 hours, centrifuged and adjusted to pH 2
194 using concentrated nitric acid.

195 *EDTA extraction*

196 Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) is a strong chelating agent that removes trace
197 elements associated with stable binding sites in the soil matrix. It can extract trace
198 elements bound to organic matter and mineral phases such as oxy-hydroxides and clay
199 minerals (Quevauviller et al., 1998; Feng et al., 2005; Madejón et al., 2011; Monterroso
200 et al., 2014; Adamo et al., 2018). EDTA extractions have been used to assess metals
201 potentially able to move into the plant root system. However, several authors also have
202 pointed its ability to extract As bound to iron oxy-hydroxides (Wenzel et al., 2001;
203 Madejón et al., 2011). 10 ml of 0.05 M ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid adjusted to 7.00
204 ± 0.05 pH with concentrated hydrochloric acid reacted with 0.4 g of soil for 1 hour, and
205 then was filtered and adjusted to pH 2 using concentrated nitric acid.

206 *Ammonium acetate extraction*

207 NH_4 -acetate has been widely used for exchangeable element determination so it has been
208 used to assess phytoavailable metals in soils (Dold, 2003; Kabata-Pendias, 2004; Anjos
209 et al., 2012; Abreu et al., 2014). A solution of 50 ml 1 M ammonium acetate was stirred
210 with 2 g of each sample during 6 hours. The solution was filtered and the pH was adjusted
211 to 2 using concentrated nitric acid.

212 *Instrumentation*

213 All extraction solutions were taken to a Bruker S2 PicoFox Total Reflection Fluorescence
214 X-ray spectrophotometer. For all analyses live time was 500 s, current was set at $600 \mu\text{A}$,
215 voltage was at 50 kV, and the excitation was with a Mo K radiation. The chemical
216 elements analysed are the same trace elements than in Section 2.2.

217

218 **3. Results and discussion**

219 3.1. Mineralogical Composition

220 All samples were mostly composed of quartz and phyllosilicates with a small amount of
221 feldspar (**Table 2**). Samples from site RT 1 were primarily composed of quartz,
222 especially the subsoil sample RT 1-2 with 92 wt% quartz detected. Calcite was detected
223 at very low content in some of the samples. This type of soil does not typically have
224 carbonates, but liming practices are commonly used for farmers to improve soil fertility
225 and prevent soil acidity (Fernández-Caliani et al., 2009; Madejón et al., 2011). Hematite
226 was detected at the subsoil from sites 3, 4, and 5. Goethite, a very common mineral in
227 this environment, is quite probably present in the soils, but due to its low content it could
228 not be detected by XRD (Bigham et al., 1996; Dold, 2003).

229 The clay mineralogy was found to have mostly illite (<45 wt%), accompanied by
230 kaolinite (5-11 wt%), and trace amounts of chlorite (<5 wt%). Illite was found to be more
231 abundant in topsoil samples, while kaolinite was in subsoils, especially in site 4, where
232 it was present in higher proportions than illite. The presence of chlorite seemed to allow
233 the formation of illite-chlorite interlayers (type corrensite) in trace amounts.

234

235 3.2. Soil Parameters

236 Edaphic parameters are shown in **Table 3**. The soil texture was silty loam, except for
237 samples RT 1-1 (sandy loam) and RT 1-2 (loamy sand), consistently with their higher
238 content in quartz and their location at the top of a hill. The soil pH varied from
239 circumneutral (6.9, site 3) to moderately acidic (5.3-5.8, sites 1 and 2). In general, pH
240 values were more acidic in the topsoil than in the subsoil of each sampling plot, which is
241 a result of a sum of factors as the deposition of atmospheric acidifying gases, the acid
242 rainfall reinforced by the spread of mine particles over soils, the agricultural practices that
243 acidify the soil by the application of fertilizers, the nutrient uptake by crops, and the
244 mineralization of organic matter (Goulding, 2016).

245 The carbonate content was low (<1.6 wt%) in all the samples, as expected by the
246 mineralogical composition of the soils. Unlike the low levels of carbonates, all samples
247 were found to have relatively high levels of organic matter (mean value of 9.7 wt%)
248 (**Table 3**). These values were higher than others found in minesoils of the Riotinto area

249 (Fernández-Caliani et al., 2009), but similar to those found in other garden soils (Madejón
250 et al., 2011). Organic matter distributed preferably on topsoil, consistent with them being
251 agricultural plots (Madejón et al., 2011). Organic matter can act as a sorption tool for
252 some PTEs by forming complexes (Madeira et al., 2012, Gabarrón et al., 2018). In acidic
253 soils, such as those of the present study, organic matter has been found to compete with
254 As for adsorption sites (Wang and Mulligan, 2006).

255 Amorphous and crystalline iron oxy-hydroxides extracted were found to be relatively
256 high for sites 2, 3, 4, and 5 and moderate for site 1 (**Table 3**). The amorphous phase was
257 higher at the topsoil, while the crystalline iron oxides were more abundant at the subsoil,
258 particularly in samples 3-2, 4-2 and 5-2, where hematite was detected by XRD (**Table2**).

259

260 3.3. Chemical composition of soils

261 Major element concentrations expressed in weight percentage of oxides can be seen in
262 **Table 1**. All samples were low in alkaline and alkaline earth metals, with MgO and Na₂O
263 being below 2 wt% and K₂O around 3 wt%. Calcium content was also low, which was
264 consistent with the low calcite and carbonate content. The higher contents of calcium
265 appeared in the higher soil levels. Iron oxide concentration was around 7-8 wt% and
266 alumina around 15 wt%. Sulfur was present in soils with concentrations below 1 wt%
267 SO₃. The lowest values of major elements were found in site 1, particularly in the subsoil
268 sample (RT 1-2), where silica content was the highest (85.49 wt%).

269 Total concentrations of the main trace elements (**Table 1**) are similar to previous
270 concentrations reported in the study area (Fernández-Caliani et al., 2009; Barba et al.,
271 2007; López et al., 2008; Romero et al., 2012). Cu (42-642 mg·kg⁻¹), Ni (7-83 mg·kg⁻¹)
272 and Zn (73-464 mg·kg⁻¹) exceeded the regional baseline of the SPZ, while As (20-299
273 mg·kg⁻¹) and Pb (68-631 mg·kg⁻¹) exceeded the SSL (36 and 275 mg·kg⁻¹, respectively)
274 as well. However, Cr values (14-93 mg·kg⁻¹) are lower than the regional baseline of
275 Andalusia. Previous studies have distinguished two different pedogeochemical
276 associations. As, Cu, Pb and Zn have been associated to geochemical anomalies and
277 mining activity, while Cr and Ni appear in high concentrations associated to basic rocks
278 (López et al., 2008; Fernández-Caliani et al 2009; Romero et al., 2012). High contents of
279 Cu were also influenced by the application of chemicals in agricultural practices (Romero
280 et al., 2012).

281 The lowest values of PTEs were found in site RT 1, particularly in the subsoil level
282 (sample RT 1-2). This can be associated to the higher concentration of sand in this site,
283 which also affects the mobility of trace elements. Sandier soil favors the mobility of PTEs
284 because it has a lower sorption capacity (González et al., 2011). The highest values of
285 PTEs were found in site RT 3, located at the bottom of a valley next to the mining area,
286 which could have been contaminated by mining spills. However, samples from sites 4
287 and 5, located far away from the mining influence, also showed high values of trace
288 elements, so more samples are necessary to determine the local background in order to
289 assess the anthropogenic contamination. The concentrations of PTEs in the topsoil were
290 similar or slightly higher than the contents in the subsoil.

291 Correlations between concentrations of PTEs, major elements, and soil parameters are
292 shown in **Table 4**. Most of the PTEs showed strong correlations such as Pb-Zn ($r = 0.96$),
293 Cu-Zn ($r = 0.91$), As-Pb ($r = 0.81$), Cr-Cu ($r = 0.89$), suggesting that they are related to a
294 similar source or geochemical process (Loredo-Portales et al., 2017).

295 Cr, Cu, and Zn were strongly correlated with total Fe_2O_3 and extracted iron (amorphous
296 and crystalline), showing the ability of Fe oxy-hydroxides for trace element sorption
297 (Galán et al., 2003). Surprisingly, the correlations of Pb and As were lower, although
298 these elements usually have been associated to iron oxides (Bigham et al., 1996; Dold,
299 2003; Galán et al., 2003).

300 Strong correlations were also found between trace elements and soil texture, especially
301 for Cr, Cu, and Zn. Silt and clay fractions include reactive components such as clay
302 minerals and other phyllosilicates, iron oxy-hydroxides, carbonates, and organic matter
303 that promote the sorption of those metals. Chromium, Cu, and Zn were also significantly
304 correlated with aluminum, which is representative of the phyllosilicate content,
305 suggesting that they could be adsorbed on the surface of illite, kaolinite, or chlorite (Gier
306 and Johns, 2000). The strong correlation of Cr with Al_2O_3 ($r = 0.98$), Fe_2O_3 ($r = 0.96$),
307 and SiO_2 ($r = -0.92$) suggests it is related to phyllosilicates rich in Fe, such as chlorite,
308 probably as a source of the element instead of as a sorbing mineral.

309 The correlations of trace elements with the pH were not significant. However, a new
310 statistical analysis performed avoiding the anomalous sample RT 1-2 (with high pH and
311 quartz content) gave positive correlations for Cu, Pb, and Zn ($R > 0.83$). The results show
312 the importance of this factor controlling the mobility of heavy metals, which promotes

313 their adsorption and accumulation in soils at high pH (Adriano, 2001; Goulding, 2016;
314 Romero et al., 2018). No correlations were found with the organic matter content, even
315 though it is an important factor contributing to the cation exchange capacity of soils.

316 In summary, Cr, a typical geogenic element in this area, seems to be related to
317 phyllosilicates as chlorite, while As, Cu, Pb, and Zn, which can be anthropogenic
318 elements, show two different behavior. Zinc and Cu are more mobile elements, especially
319 under acidic pH (Adriano, 2001), so their concentrations were related to the pH and
320 sorption capacity of the soil provided by the iron oxy-hydroxides content and the texture.
321 On the other hand, As and Pb, which are more immobile elements, showed lower
322 correlations with the edaphic parameters.

323

324 3.4. Trace element mobility

325 The different extractions remove the trace elements from different compartments and they
326 are usefull to assess the mobility and bioavailability of PTEs under different
327 environmental conditions. The water-soluble fractions respresent how the elements may
328 move during rain or irrigation and the proportion that is easily available for plants. The
329 amounts extracted were below $1 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ in most of the cases, except for Cu and As, the
330 last reaching $4.3 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ in sample RT 3-2 (**Table 5**). These results represent 0.6 to 1.5
331 wt% of total As, (Figure 2), which was the most mobile element in water. Although, in
332 general, the slightly acidic pH of soils prevents As mobilization, these conditions favor
333 the organic matter to be sorbed to metal hydroxides, forming negatively charged surfaces
334 and inhibing the adsorption of As anions (Wang and Mulligan, 2006). A principal
335 component analysis (PCA) performed with percentages of extracted elements and soil
336 parameters showed a negative relationship between As and pH (Figure 3a), suggesting
337 that acidic conditions may promote As availability by the competition with organic matter
338 for the sorption sites. Concerning Cu and Zn, the highest water-soluble fractions were
339 extracted from site 1, especially from the subsoil (Figure 2), accordingly with the edaphic
340 parametes found and the low sorption capacity of this sample. Consistently, the PCA
341 showed that water soluble metals were positively correlated with the content of sand, and
342 negatively with iron oxy-hydroxides (Figure 3a).

343 Ammonium acetate extractions showed that Cu, Ni and Zn are the main elements in the
344 exchangeable fraction (**Table 5**), so they can be available for plant uptake (Kabata-

345 Pendias, 2004; Anjos et al., 2012). The amounts extracted were usually below $8 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$.
346 Arsenic was also extracted in samples RT 2-1 ($11.1 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$) RT 3-1 ($5.1 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$) and
347 RT 3-2 ($8.3 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$) (**Table 5**). The percentages extracted were below 3 wt% in most of
348 the cases (Figure 2). However, in sample RT 1-2, the mobilizable fraction of Cu, Ni and
349 Zn was 15-25 wt%, which is consistent with the low adsorption capacity of that soil. The
350 PCA showed, again, that the fraction of metals extracted with ammonium acetate,
351 particularly the most mobile such as Zn, Ni, and Cu, was higher from sandy soils and
352 lower from soils rich in sorbing components such as iron oxy-hydroxides (Figure 4b).
353 The available fraction of more immobile elements, such as Pb and As, partially seemed to
354 be affected by the pH.

355 EDTA extractions removed Cu, Pb, and Zn in concentrations that exceeded $100 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$
356 in several samples and As up to $30.9 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ in sample RT 3-2 (**Table 5**). The values are
357 close to the SSL of Andalusia ($36.9 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$). The fractions extracted were below 10 wt%
358 for As, but they were higher for Cu, Pb, and Zn, ranging between 10-35 wt% (Figure 2).
359 Although Pb is usually quite immobile, the results show that there is an important labile
360 pool of this metal. EDTA is a chelant extracting elements associated to carbonates, but
361 also bound to organic matter or adsorbed to Fe-oxides (Quevauviller et al., 1998; Gleyzes
362 et al., 2002). The results suggest that a great proportion of As, Cu, Pb, and Zn can be
363 bound to organic matter and iron oxy-hydroxides. Although the first two factors of the
364 PCA explain less than 65 wt% of the variance, the results suggest again that high contents
365 of silty and clayey fractions and iron oxy-hydroxides decrease the available fractions of
366 Cu, Cr, and Zn (Figure 3d).

367 Finally, monoammonium phosphate is useful to assess the availability of As, since
368 phosphate competes with As for sorption sites (Wenzel et al., 2001). The extractions
369 reached up to $28.5 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ in site 3, $11 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ in site 2 and $6.5 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ in site 4 (**Table**
370 **5**). The percentages extracted were also high in those sites, with fractions ranging from
371 6.6 wt% (RT 4-2) to 13 wt% (RT 2-1) (Figure 2). The results are interesting since
372 phosphate fertilizers can be applied to the garden soils, which may enhance the
373 availability of As. The PCA suggests that the extractable As with monoammonium
374 phosphated was removed from organic matter, and again it was promoted under acidic
375 conditions (Figure 4c). However, considering that the loading of As is small, more data
376 is necessary.

377 In summary, the mobility assays show that the extracted amounts of PTEs tend to increase
378 along with their total content in soil, as occur in sample RT 3. These logical results have
379 been seen before by many other studies (e.g. Adamo et al., 2014). However, the highest
380 extracted percentages of Cu, Ni and Zn were found in sample RT 2-2, which had the
381 lowest total trace element concentration but the lower adsorption capacity. This confirm
382 that soil properties such as pH, texture or OM play an important role in the adsorption
383 capacity of the soil (McLaughlin et al., 2000; Clemente et al., 2008; Adamo et al., 2014).
384 Although most of the samples exceeded the regional baseline and SSL, the general low
385 bioavailability suggests that they do not necessary pose a risk to human health. This is
386 particularly true for essential micronutrients such as Cr, Cu or Zn, and very immobile
387 elements such us Pb. Other studies with similar available fractions showed low transfer
388 factors to plants, with concentration in edible vegetables below the maximum allowable
389 levels (McLaughlin et al., 2001; Abreu et al., 2014; Adamo et al., 2014; Antoniadis et al.,
390 2017). Concerning As, which showed the highest water and monoammonium phosphate
391 soluble fractions, more studies are necessary to assess its transfer to vegetables and its
392 possible human health risk.

393

394 **4. Conclusions**

395 Soils of family gardens close to the Riotinto mines showed high concentrations of
396 potentially toxic elements (PTEs) well above the regional baseline of the South
397 Portuguese Zone. Some of them, such as As, Pb, and Cu also surpassed the screening soil
398 levels established for Andalusia in many samples, independent of the distance to the
399 mining area. Therefore, a deeper investigation and a more widespread sampling are
400 necessary in order to determine the local background before to assess the contamination
401 of soils.

402 Total content of trace elements in soil showed some correlations with edaphic parameters.
403 Chromium was associated with trace phyllosilicates such as chlorite. Total concentrations
404 of Cu and Zn were associated to high pH, silty-clayey fractions, and iron oxy-hydroxides
405 content. Arsenic and Pb showed lower correlations.

406 Concerning the mobility, As was the most mobile element with water extractions,
407 probably because under acidic pH organic matter competes with As for sorption sites. On
408 the other hand, mobility of metals increased in sandy soil samples and decreased with the

409 content in iron oxy-hydroxides, especially for Cu, Cr, and Zn in water-soluble and
410 ammonium acetate-extractable fractions.

411 A great fraction of As and metals such as Cu, Pb, and Zn, probably bound to organic
412 matter or iron oxy-hydroxides, were extracted with monoammonium phosphate and
413 EDTA, respectively. In site 3, the amounts of As removed with both extractants (around
414 $30 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$) were close to the SSLs of Andalusia. The high content of As extracted with
415 monoammonium phosphate should be considered by farmers when phosphate fertilizers
416 are applied to soil.

417 Although most of the plots had very high total levels of As and metals and high amounts
418 were extracted with monoammonium phosphate and EDTA in several cases, the most
419 labile pool of trace elements mobilizable with water and ammonium acetate was low. The
420 results suggest that they are not necessarily a risk to humans due to very little of the trace
421 elements potentially going into the trophic chain. These results strongly demonstrate that
422 higher investigation efforts have to be done by governing bodies in order to obtain real
423 risk values for trace elements that respect and take into consideration the local geology
424 of the zone. Moreover, the use of total concentrations should be avoided since it may
425 create social alarm. Conversely, the mobility, the bioaccessibility and the transfer to plants
426 and trophic chain are encouraged to be included in contamination assessment procedures,
427 since they can show the fraction that could be digested and produce a real health risk.

428

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434

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589

590 **Captions for tables and figures**

591 **Table 1.** Major elements (wt%) and trace element concentrations ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$) of soil
592 samples and comparison with the Andalusian baseline (And), South Portuguese Zone
593 baseline (SPZ), and the SSL of Andalusia. Data for SSL from the Real Decreto 18/2015
594 and for the SPZ and Andalusia baseline from Galán et al. (2008).

595 **Table 2.** Semiquantitative mineral composition in wt% ($\pm 5\%$)

596 **Table 3.** Results for soil parameters (wt% except for depth in cm and pH).

597 **Table 4.** Pearson's correlation coefficients for soil parameters, major elements and trace
598 elements. Values in bold are significant at $P < 0.01$.

599 **Table 5:** Iron and trace element concentration extracted with water, monoammonium
600 phosphate, ammonium acetate and EDTA (data in $\text{mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$)

601 **Figure 1.** Study area and sampling location

602 **Figure 2.** Percentages of PTEs extracted with deionized water, monoammonium
603 phosphate, ammonium acetate and EDTA

604 **Figure 3.** Principal components analysis of the percentages of trace elements extracted
605 and soil parameters. a) water; b) ammonium acetate; c) monoammonium phosphate; d)
606 EDTA. (FOH: Fe oxy-hydroxides)

607

608

Table 1. Major elements (wt%) and trace element concentrations (mg·kg⁻¹) of soil samples and comparison with the Andalusian baseline (And), the South Portuguese Zone baseline (SPZ), and the SSL of Andalusia. Data for SSL from the Real Decreto 18/2015 and for the SPZ and Andalusia baseline from Galán et al. (2008).

Sample	Depth (cm)	Al ₂ O ₃	CaO	Fe ₂ O ₃	K ₂ O	MgO	Na ₂ O	P ₂ O ₅	SO ₃	SiO ₂	TiO ₂	As	Cr	Cu	Ni	Pb	Zn
D.L		0.01	0.04	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.02	1.1	1.0	1.8	0.1	3.8	11.2
Q.L		0.02	0.05	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.07	0.03	3.9	4.0	8.1	0.5	5.8	12.3
R.E.		0.02	0.04	0.05	0.03	0.01	0.04	0.02	0.09	0.04	0.03	0.22	0.12	0.08	0.03	0.13	0.10
RT1-1	0-20	10.13	2.78	4.58	2.59	0.81	0.32	1.10	0.62	63.64	0.70	35	34	121	21	154	173
RT1-2	20-40	6.63	0.45	1.73	1.25	0.45	0.30	0.39	0.12	85.49	0.38	20	14	42	7	68	73
RT2-1	0-20	16.34	1.22	6.95	3.52	1.21	0.53	0.71	0.52	46.21	0.93	88	81	363	83	233	282
RT2-2	20-40	17.99	1.06	7.38	3.73	1.28	0.62	0.73	0.30	50.25	0.97	99	86	402	82	284	289
RT3-1	0-20	16.06	2.41	8.62	3.31	1.24	0.67	1.33	0.65	50.19	0.90	330	89	642	51	631	464
RT3-2	20-40	15.57	2.67	8.74	3.23	1.31	0.71	1.42	0.62	49.35	0.88	300	85	618	51	544	454
RT4-1	0-20	16.65	2.35	7.73	3.35	1.13	0.57	0.87	0.35	50.10	1.03	95	91	464	39	542	408
RT4-2	20-40	17.04	2.11	8.16	3.20	1.13	0.65	0.80	0.25	52.37	1.00	99	93	492	39	467	434
RT5-1	0-20	15.42	2.07	6.99	2.93	1.23	0.58	1.01	0.37	51.86	0.95	79	76	520	35	240	268
RT5-2	20-40	16.31	1.82	7.22	3.00	1.28	0.59	0.99	0.27	54.32	1.00	89	84	431	38	287	281
And	0-20											10	70	24	29	24	56
SPZ	0-20											25	95	32	35	38	76
SSL												36	10,000	595	1,530	275	10,000

D.L.: detection limit; Q.L.: quantification limit; R.E.: relative error; values in bold are higher than SPZ. Bold underlined values are higher than Andalusia SSL.

1

2

3 **Table 2.** Semiquantitative mineral composition in wt% ($\pm 5\%$).

Sample	Depth (cm)	Total mineralogy (wt%)					Clay mineralogy (total wt%)		
		Q	Fds	Cal	Hem	Phy	I	KI	Chl
RT 1-1	0-20	76	tr	tr	-	22	17	5	tr
RT 1-2	20-40	92	tr	-	-	6	tr	tr	-
RT 2-1	0-20	38	6	-	-	56	49	7	tr
RT 2-2	20-40	30	5	-	-	44	38	6	tr
RT 3-1	0-20	48	7	-	-	46	38	8	tr
RT 3-2	20-40	46	8	tr	tr	45	35	10	tr
RT 4-1	0-20	40	tr	-	-	55	45	10	tr
RT 4-2	20-40	40	5	tr	tr	55	14	41	tr
RT 5-1	0-20	47	6	tr	-	47	36	11	tr
RT 5-2	20-40	50	5	tr	tr	45	34	11	tr

4 Q: quartz; Fds: feldspar; Cal: calcite; Hem: hematite; Phy: phyllosilicates; I: illite; Kaol:
5 kaolinite; Chl: chlorite; tr: traces (<5 wt%)

6

7

8

9 **Table 3.** Results for soil parameters .

Sample	Depth cm	Sand wt%	Silt wt%	Clay wt%	pH	Carbonates (CaCO ₃) wt%	Organic matter wt%	Amorphous	Crystalline
								Iron oxy- hydroxides wt%	Iron oxy- hydroxides wt%
RT 1-1	0-20	58	39	3	5.3	1.1	10.0	3.1	0.4
RT 1-2	20-40	77	21	2	6.6	0.8	5.2	2.2	0.8
RT 2-1	0-20	39	58	3	5.7	0.9	15.0	5.2	1.2
RT 2-2	20-40	41	56	3	5.8	1.2	9.3	5.0	2.5
RT 3-1	0-20	29	67	4	6.6	0.6	9.2	6.0	2.5
RT 3-2	20-40	28	67	5	6.9	1.2	9.3	5.1	3.1
RT 4-1	0-20	35	60	5	6.5	1.6	11.0	4.1	2.4
RT 4-2	20-40	21	70	9	6.7	0.9	9.4	4.2	3.0
RT 5-1	0-20	28	67	5	6.3	1.0	11.0	4.4	2.1
RT 5-2	20-40	31	65	5	6.3	1.0	9.0	3.9	3.0

10

Table 4. Pearson's correlation coefficients for soil parameters, major elements and trace elements. Values in bold are significant at P < 0.01.

	pH	Carb	OM	Am Fe	Cr Fe	silt+clay	Al ₂ O ₃	CaO	Fe ₂ O ₃	SO ₃	SiO ₂	As	Cr	Cu	Ni	Pb	Zn
pH	1.00																
Carb	-0.09	1.00															
OM	-0.44	0.20	1.00														
Am Fe	0.12	-0.11	0.52	1.00													
Cr Fe	0.63	0.17	-0.03	0.54	1.00												
silt+clay	0.34	0.09	0.44	0.74	0.83	1.00											
Al ₂ O ₃	0.11	0.25	0.55	0.79	0.76	0.89	1.00										
CaO	0.09	0.26	0.23	0.29	0.29	0.52	0.27	1.00									
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.28	0.19	0.47	0.85	0.81	0.95	0.92	0.54	1.00								
SO ₃	-0.22	-0.06	0.45	0.57	-0.07	0.26	0.16	0.68	0.41	1.00							
SiO ₂	0.03	-0.26	-0.73	-0.85	-0.60	-0.87	-0.94	-0.47	-0.93	-0.46	1.00						
As	0.51	-0.20	0.01	0.76	0.55	0.53	0.40	0.47	0.66	0.63	-0.47	1.00					
Cr	0.27	0.22	0.50	0.81	0.82	0.93	0.98	0.35	0.96	0.20	-0.92	0.51	1.00				
Cu	0.50	0.04	0.31	0.84	0.84	0.92	0.82	0.49	0.94	0.36	-0.81	0.77	0.89	1.00			
Ni	-0.25	0.08	0.64	0.79	0.32	0.46	0.74	-0.13	0.60	0.29	-0.75	0.32	0.66	0.46	1.00		
Pb	0.58	0.15	0.13	0.68	0.73	0.72	0.63	0.59	0.83	0.40	-0.63	0.81	0.75	0.85	0.27	1.00	
Zn	0.50	0.14	0.29	0.77	0.79	0.86	0.77	0.59	0.93	0.41	-0.77	0.76	0.86	0.91	0.42	0.96	1.00

Table 5: Iron and trace element concentration extracted with water, monoammonium phosphate, ammonium acetate and EDTA (data in mg·kg⁻¹-soil)

	Fe	As	Cr	Cu	Ni	Pb	Zn
Water soluble							
DL	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
RT 1-1	12.4	0.52	n.d.	1.00	0.10	0.10	0.92
RT 1-2	25.0	0.28	0.10	0.51	0.06	0.11	0.69
RT 2-1	11.5	1.35	n.d.	1.30	0.17	0.09	0.46
RT 2-2	62.2	1.22	0.16	1.80	0.17	0.37	1.12
RT 3-1	17.5	2.81	0.07	1.50	0.06	0.22	1.47
RT 3-2	26.4	4.25	0.06	2.20	0.07	0.32	0.92
RT 4-1	13.1	0.86	0.15	0.70	0.07	0.27	0.84
RT 4-2	10.5	0.77	n.d.	0.70	0.03	0.32	0.54
RT 5-1	12.0	0.50	0.05	1.10	0.04	0.08	0.57
RT 5-2	17.4	0.65	0.04	1.20	0.05	0.14	0.47
Monoammonium phosphate extractable							
DL	0.08	0.05	0.13	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
RT 1-1	11.80	1.50	0.22	48.2	0.12	0.26	12.30
RT 1-2	9.00	1.00	n.d.	2.2	0.13	0.59	2.70
RT 2-1	4.90	11.00	0.38	3.1	0.71	0.05	2.20
RT 2-2	12.40	9.60	n.d.	6.7	0.73	0.16	3.20
RT 3-1	4.40	28.50	n.d.	11	0.21	0.08	3.30
RT 3-2	3.60	27.80	n.d.	5.3	0.22	0.15	1.60
RT 4-1	2.10	6.50	n.d.	1.9	n.d.	n.d.	1.20
RT 4-2	2.30	6.50	n.d.	1.7	0.07	0.09	1.90
RT 5-1	6.10	2.20	n.d.	2.8	0.15	0.09	2.30
RT 5-2	5.60	3.10	n.d.	3.8	0.10	0.08	1.80
Ammonium acetate extractable							
DL	0.13	0.05	0.2	0.08	0.08	0.05	0.08
RT 1-1	15.30	1.00	n.d.	3.62	0.82	0.82	10.00
RT 1-2	32.50	1.20	n.d.	6.75	1.80	0.64	15.00
RT 2-1	7.32	11.10	n.d.	6.73	3.20	2.61	4.80
RT 2-2	14.10	0.90	n.d.	6.53	1.10	0.67	7.50
RT 3-1	12.40	5.10	n.d.	7.40	0.64	0.86	7.80
RT 3-2	14.40	8.30	n.d.	9.02	0.76	0.64	8.10
RT 4-1	8.30	1.10	n.d.	3.04	0.25	0.77	4.00
RT 4-2	14.10	1.40	n.d.	5.95	0.62	1.40	7.30
RT 5-1	12.60	0.80	n.d.	5.06	0.38	1.10	6.90
RT 5-2	12.80	1.10	n.d.	6.01	0.42	1.00	7.70

EDTA-extractable

DL	0.1	0.03	0.20	0.08	0.08	0.05	0.05
RT 1-1	553.0	3.10	0.88	35.60	2.36	37.60	53.90
RT 1-2	219.0	1.30	0.81	15.10	0.56	18.10	15.00
RT 2-1	1155.0	8.50	2.34	82.60	8.76	47.30	35.70
RT 2-2	601.0	4.00	1.35	94.90	9.83	47.40	35.70
RT 3-1	996.0	23.60	1.90	122.00	2.94	62.60	71.60
RT 3-2	1312.0	30.90	2.70	153.00	3.88	76.80	101.80
RT 4-1	426.0	6.00	1.00	104.00	0.62	136.00	39.20
RT 4-2	294.0	5.40	0.70	120.00	0.50	150.00	42.60
RT 5-1	540.0	1.80	1.10	81.20	0.79	56.80	53.50
RT 5-2	645.0	3.30	1.20	116.00	1.24	73.30	63.90

n.d.: not detected.

Monoammonium phosphate

EDTA

Figure 3

[Click here to access/download;Figure;Figure 3.eps](#)

